

“A Study on Consumer Perception towards Stone Products With Special Reference to Royal Stone Park in Madurai”

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Introduction

The study was undertaken to analyze the concept of Consumer Perception in meeting the objectives of an organization and to adopt the best practices of the industry to serve the customer.

“The theory without practical is lame and practical without theory is blind.”

The study conducted in Madurai with special reference to stone product users, to analysis the Consumer Perception about stone products and finding the suggestion to give best suggestion to Company.

Perception

Perception is a process by which consumers interpret the meaning (subconsciously) of their sensations. This means that their sensations are derived from our five senses. Solomon et al.(2002 p.36-51) have explored this more detailed and explored that consumers trust their senses, however different people interpret stimuli’s differently therefore the meaning varies as well. The overview of the perceptual process help to identify how the perception process works and it is quiet straightforward (Appendix C). The awareness of perception process can help implementing store, brand and product images and positioning (Bohdanowicz and Clamp 1994)

The Consumer Perception Process

The perception process as displayed in Figure 3.2 consists of five distinct activities. The first activity is that of exposure to stimuli. The second states that attention to stimuli has to occur. During the third activity, organisation, people organise stimuli so that it can be comprehended and retained.

The fourth activity is that of interpretation of the message. Information is retained during the last activity. As seen in Figure a successful perception process leads to a purchasing and consumption decision.

Objectives of Study

- The primary objective is to study the consumer perception towards Royal Stone Park in Madurai city.
- To study the respondents preference towards Natural Stone Work products.
- To study the factors that influences the customers in purchase of Natural stones.

Scope of the Study

The study aims to find out how Consumer perceive the organized Natural stone and the promotional efforts taken by the Royal Stone Park.

Literature Review

Adilla Anggraeni and et.al. (2015) in their study about effect of brand experience, level of satisfaction, trust on customers' loyalty was analyzed using regression analysis. Perception for the brand is developed when the customers prefer to buy the product and experience the positive for the same

Ankit and Nikha (2014) the purpose of the study to find the various factors that influence the buying behavior of the consumer before making the purchase decision to purchase the product. The continuous improvements in the product will lead to increase in the level of satisfaction of the consumer and the company can retain the existing customer including opening the doors for the potential customers.

Harish Naik and Ramesh Olekar (2012) study refers that the buying behavior has psychological, social impact. According to the authors the customer is an important visitor of any marketer because the consumer is doing a favor by purchasing the required product and giving the opportunity to serve him/her to fulfil the satisfaction level.

Industry Profile

Stone is the world's original building and memorial material. It has been used for thousands of years and most of the oldest, remaining structures in the world are made from stone. Stone continues to be used in and on new structures. Its natural beauty and enduring quality is highly preferred.

Many economies have emerged from the global economic recession and the use of natural stone is resurging, continuing the trend and desire for natural stone begun centuries ago.

Some consumption trends are especially important to be taking into account: the diversification of usage of natural stone and stone products; the renewed interest of consumers in natural stone, more and more perceived as an affordable luxury; the changing taste of consumers in terms of colors, design and material; the high expectations in terms of quality and standards

Company Profile

Royal Stone Park Madurai in purist of excellence is committed to comply with applicable requirements for developing and providing designing Products at on affordable cost. Royal stone park is a leading company for designing, Supplying, trading and exporting Marble statue and Handmade Kitchen Stone, stone Lamp, Stone Chair, Building Elevation & Garden which is located at Madurai, Tamilnadu, India.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. Respondents Opinion About Natural Stone Products

Table 1 Opinion about Natural Stone Product

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	48	96.0
	No	2	4.0
	Total	50	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

Table 1 shows that about, 96% of respondents like Natural stone products and 4% of the respondents doesn’t like .

2. Opinion of the Facilities In Royal Stone Park

Table 2 Opinion about the facilities in Royal stone park

	Frequency	Percent
Credit Facility	5	10.0
Transportation facility	7	14.0
Delivery Service	29	58.0
Direct Purchase	9	18.0
Total	50	100.0

Interpretation

The above table shows that out of 50 respondents 58% of the respondents liked Delivery service and 18% of the respondent are liked direct purchase, 14% of respondents are liked Transportation facility and remaining 5% are liked Credit facility.

Correlation

Monthly Family Income and Level of Price

		Family Income	For Price
Family Income	Pearson Correlation	1	-.298*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.036
	N	50	50
For Price	Pearson Correlation	-.298*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.036	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Inference

The correlation value from the Monthly family income and level of price is near to value – 0.298 so it is Negative correlated one.

ANOVA

The One way ANOVA Calculated between frequently visit & Comparison to other Company.

Table

ANOVA					
How frequently visit					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.600	2	.300	.709	.498
Within Groups	19.900	48	.423		
Total	20.500	50			

Inference

The above table shows the Relation between group and within groups. The perception level of consumer in comparison to the other company and Frequently visit value is + .498 so, it is strongly related.

Findings

- 96% of the respondents are prefer to like Natural stone products.
- 66% of the respondents are Factors influenced by Royal Stone Park is Relatives and Friends.
- 56% of respondents are Agree the Natural Stone Products Design & quality being good.
- The correlation value from the Monthly family income and Importance level of price the is near to value – 0.298 so it is Negative correlated one.
- The perception level of consumer in comparison to the other company and Frequently visit value is + .498 so, it is strongly related.

Suggestion

- The Royal Stone Park should improve their Awareness level of stone products.
- Company can improve delivery service for huge purchase.
- Company can convert the customers into publicity agents. Develop an incentive for them to endorsement from them is more effective than any amount of advertising - and it is much cheaper.

Conclusion

The Perception is important factor of an organization. From the study the process of consumer perception and its effectiveness is understood, the perception of Consumer about the Natural stone product is revealed.

The study is conducted to know the Consumer perception level of Natural stone product given to organization. And it can take steps to increase the productivity. Through this project, this project gained a good practical exposure to meet different kinds of Consumer and their response towards the various aspects (such as Satisfaction level of Company Location, Awareness, Range of product satisfaction). As to conclude the Royal Stone Park, management can kindly consider the above suggestion to build a positive Perception in the minds of the Consumer.

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